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EURO-LABS

EUROpean Laboratories for Accelerator Based Science
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DELIVERABLE REPORT

ALL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES VIDEOS COMPLETED

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Abstract:

This document reports on the production of short videos to present and publicize the Research Infrastructures involved in the EURO-LABS project, in order to attract a wider range of potential users. Communication and dissemination of exchange opportunities is strategic to increase the usage of the facilities by a larger number of researchers, with emphasis on young researchers.

EURO-LABS Consortium, 2024

For more information on EURO-LABS, its partners and contributors please see <https://web.infn.it/EURO-LABS/>

The EUROpean Laboratories for Accelerator Based Science (EURO-LABS) project has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme dedicated to Research Infrastructure (RI) services advancing frontier knowledge under Grant Agreement no. 101057511. EURO-LABS began in September 2022 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

One of the activities planned within WP5 is the production of short videos of the Research Infrastructures providing transnational access within the EURO-LABS project. This activity is important in order to publicize the activities within the facilities and the Transnational and Virtual Access opportunities offered by the project.

These videos target in particular young researchers and/or new users interested in accessing these installations for the first time and this information will help them to select the optimal infrastructure where to carry out their experiments or tests. Visits by the INFN Multimedia group were made for filming at the different facilities. To date the INFN Multimedia Group has produced 34 videos, combining already-existing footage (suitably updated and made compatible) from installations with new original videos. The filming of 5 RIs was not possible so far for various reasons like the facilities being upgraded and 3 facilities which could not be completed (such a possibility was mentioned in MS34). However suitable action has been planned for the latter videos to be released within 6 months. The videos have been published on the EURO-LABS website and also at the INFN Multimedia official repository and they will also be used by the other EURO-LABS partners and included on their websites. The videos are stored in the INFN repository Mediawall

(https://mediawall.infn.it/view/?catName=euro-labs&lang=en_US) and they are available on the EURO-LABS website: <https://web.infn.it/EURO-LABS/> (upper menu).

1. INTRODUCTION

The core activity of the EURO-LABS project is to provide and support Transnational and Virtual Access to a network of Research Infrastructures (RIs) in the fields of Nuclear Physics and of accelerator and detector technology for High Energy Physics. These research communities work with a large number of varied RIs. Communication and dissemination of opportunities are therefore strategic to increase the usage of the facilities by a larger number of researchers, with an emphasis on young researchers and new users. The project's dissemination in this direction includes among others producing short video presentations of the RIs involved in the project. A few of existing material for a facility has been reused, updating and adapting it to the characteristics of EURO-LABS.

2. OBJECTIVE AND TARGET

The videos give an overview of the Research Infrastructures offering Transnational Access in the EURO-LABS project framework. They are also used in dissemination/communication activities organized by all EURO-LABS partners and included on their websites.

3. THE VIDEOS: WORKFLOW AND STATUS

3.1. THE WORKING FLOW

The videos have been produced by the INFN Bologna Multimedia Group, in cooperation with partners' media teams in certain cases. Active collaboration and intense dialogue with the Facility Coordinators were necessary throughout the process. Various visits for filming the videos were made by the INFN Multimedia Group in four countries (France, Germany, Poland and Sweden) so far.

Thirteen of the videos have been filmed by the INFN Multimedia Group while the other videos relied on existing materials that have been reused when possible, ensuring consistency and uniformity of style. Thus, certain facilities either produced new videos or reedited existing material. Common introduction and other final parts were inserted to maintain the uniformity. Also the presentation of Facility coordinators (FC) have been added to these existing videos. The audio descriptions in all the videos using a synthetic voice were produced by using texts provided by the FC.

3.2. THE VIDEOS

A detailed script is used to create the videos includes:

- An introductory part common to all EURO-LABS videos, presenting the project, and with maps geographically locating the facility.
- A detailed description of the facility:
 - o What are available instruments/accelerators and their focus,
 - o What the facility can provide to users: what users can find / do at the facility,
 - o Which technical support the users will receive,
 - o What are other tools the facility offers e.g. software...etc.
- The video final part, common to all EURO-LABS videos with: links to the site, contacts and credits.

The videos are stored in the INFN repository Mediawall

(https://mediawall.infn.it/view/?catName=euro-labs&lang=en_US) and are available on the EURO-LABS website: <https://web.infn.it/EURO-LABS/> (upper menu).

A few typical illustrations are shown below.

Fig.1 EURO-LABS website related to Transnational Access

Fig.2 EURO-LABS website specifically for facilities related to Transnational Access to facilities related to WP4.

Fig.3 A summary of the existing videos in the EURO-LABS Repository (https://mediawall.infn.it/view/?catName=euro-labs&lang=en_US)

Fig.4 Screenshot from the SPIRAL2 video: Google Earth, approaching the SPIRAL2 facility at GANIL (Caen, France)

Fig.5 The FREIA Facility, Univ. of Uppsala, Sweden

Fig. 6 - Nikolaos Charitonidis (Facility Coordinator) and Alice Goillot (Operational Manager), HiRadMat, CERN, Switzerland

Fig. 7 CLEAR Facility, CERN, Switzerland

Fig.8 LNL-NSDBF Facility, INFN, Italy

3.3. STATUS

It was mentioned on MS34 “that the complete set of films will probably take longer than the schedule for the present milestone”. The project involves 45 installations in 15 countries offering Transnational Access and Virtual Access. The three facilities offering VA and the TA facility offering theoretical support will not be filmed.

It should be noted that FREIA (Univ. of Uppsala), initially treated as three different facilities, is actually considered as one facility with 3 installations. INFN/LNS-AIPF is currently being restructured due to upgrade of the accelerators and will therefore be filmed at a later stage when the facility will be ready for use. UKRI – CLARA is currently in the commissioning phase of the upgraded installation, including the high repetition rate (S-band 400 Hz) gun, together with the Full Energy Beam Exploitation (FEBE) 250 MeV 250pC FEL experimental area. Due to access restrictions in this phase the relevant video will be done later when the facility will become operational, and open to receive the first Transnational Access users. The two facilities at PSI are not receiving funding for Transnational Access, and the facility preferred not to contribute directly to the present set of videos made in an uniform style. New videos for the three facilities THOR, UoB, IST/CLEAR) could not be made due to various constraints and the INFN multimedia team has planned its trips in the coming months for the filming of the videos in these three countries.

This possibility was already mentioned in MS34, stating that “the complete set of videos will probably take longer than the schedule for the present milestone”.

Hence, the total number of videos for the facilities available now are 34.

In summary, most of the experimental facilities in operation and offering translational access has a video at the EURO-LABS webpage describing the capabilities. These videos are of interest for the community as whole and even more for new users and young researchers.